

COVID-19 vaccine and Breastfeeding

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Abstract: COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019) spread rapidly around the globe and can cause a viral infection that exhibited different symptoms the most common of which are fever, fatigue, shortness of breath, and cough. COVID-19 has a higher mortality rate than influenza. Several COVID-19 vaccines have been produced and approved, and an efficient immunologic response to vaccination is essential to limiting the pandemic's harmful health effects. However, more widely applied to pregnant women is mRNA (Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna). As it does not contain the complete genome or live viruses, the vaccine cannot replicate and cause disease. There are a few studies regarding the safety and efficiency of vaccination in lactating women. This narrative review aims to find the impact of the COVID-19 vaccine on breastfeeding. According to the result of this study, anti-COVID-19 antibodies are transferred to breast milk after the mother is vaccinated against COVID-19. Hence, the acquisition of antibodies against COVID-19 directly through breast milk could be beneficial for infants via vertical-transmitted immunity.

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Vaccine, Breastmilk, Breastfeeding

1. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019) spread rapidly around the globe after being diagnosed in December 2019 in Wuhan, China. Coronavirus is known as severe acute respiratory syndrome *coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)*. COVID-19 can cause a viral infection that exhibited different symptoms the most common of which are fever, fatigue, shortness of breath, and cough (1). After exposure to transmissible sources, COVID-19 has an incubation period of 2 weeks.

The initial stage of the infection might be asymptomatic or respiratory tract infection symptoms. About 1 week after the beginning of symptoms, some patients may experience a rapid clinical deterioration, marked by respiratory symptoms. Last, a subsequent step in the acute development of COVID-19 has been recognized as acute respiratory disease syndrome (ARDS) (2).

COVID-19 has a higher mortality rate than influenza (3). Coronary heart disease (CHD), diabetes mellitus (MD), and Hypertension (HTN) were the most common disease in patients diagnosed with COVID-19 (4).

Women during pregnancy are more vulnerable to infections such as Corona infection due to physiological changes. Some detrimental effects of COVID-19 in pregnancy are

eclampsia, pre-eclampsia, hypertension, and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) which have a negative child and maternal outcomes (5,6).

Although during this COVID-19 pandemic, different treatment approaches have been asserted, including the privational and therapeutic effects of some vitamins and minerals on COVID-19 and some herbal medication, which has been used as an antibacterial and antiviral medication against some viruses, there are no available specific medicines as an effective treatment of COVID-19 Currently (7-9). Several COVID-19 vaccines have been produced and approved, and an efficient immunologic response to vaccination is essential to limiting the pandemic's harmful health effects (10). However, more widely applied to pregnant women are mRNA (Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna). As it does not contain the complete genome or live viruses, the vaccine cannot replicate and cause disease. mRNA is not able to be integrated into the host genome and it is degraded in about 2 days naturally (11,12).

Breastfeeding should be started in the first hours after delivery as it may be a protective factor against some diseases including infectious, cardiovascular diseases, leukemia, inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), necrotizing enterocolitis, atopic diseases, and coeliac disease. Moreover, Breastfeeding

has a beneficial effect on the development of the nervous system, boosting IQ and could drop the risk of some disorders such as behavioral disorders, generalized developmental disorders (GDD), and attention disorders. Furthermore, breastfeeding has other positive impacts including reducing the use of breastmilk formulas, health costs, quality-adjusted life years, and premature deaths. On the other hand, the use of breastmilk formulas may increase some risks such as oral cavity disorders. Moreover, the intestinal microbiota, thermoregulation of babies, and oxygenation could be negatively impacted by the use of breastmilk formulas (13,14). Hence, as mentioned above, Breastfeeding has a crucial effect on the infant.

WHO recommends that mothers with suspected or confirmed COVID-19 should be encouraged to continue to breastfeed because the benefits of breastfeeding substantially outweigh the potential risks for transmission (15).

CDC recommends that lactating women get vaccinated and then COVID-19 booster shots based on the evidence that COVID-19 vaccines cannot cause COVID-19 and anti-COVID-19 antibodies in their breastmilk, which could help protect their babies. However, they emphasized that More data are needed to determine what level of protection these antibodies might provide to the baby (16).

There are a few studies regarding the safety and efficiency of vaccination in lactating women. This narrative review article is conducted with the aim of finding the impact of the COVID-19 vaccine on breastfeeding.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This narrative review assessed finding impacts of the COVID-19 vaccine on breastfeeding. Relevant English publications were searched and extracted from the Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed, and Google Scholar using specific keywords including COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, vaccine, breastmilk, and breastfeeding. Unrelated and duplicate items were removed. In the next step, All the remaining articles were reviewed and after removing the irrelevant items, the results related to the selected articles in the final stage were handwritten and reviewed.

3. RESULTS

According to the statement of Italian Scientific Societies, breastfeeding must be encouraged, protected, and supported, due to the beneficial effect of breastfeeding on maternal and child health and the low risk of COVID-19 from the mother's COVID-19 vaccination. They reported that COVID-19 vaccination is currently considered compatible with breastfeeding and delays in breastfeeding may lead to the loss of its proven benefits (17).

The prospective cohort study was conducted to assess the immunogenicity of COVID-19 vaccination in lactating women. They found that after the second dose of RNA vaccine (Pfizer/BioNTech or Moderna), the COVID-19-specific immunoglobulin G increased in breastmilk and reported that Immune transfer via breastmilk to neonates occurred (18). In another prospective cohort study, eighty-four women received two doses of the RNA COVID-19 vaccine (Pfizer-BioNTech). According to the results of this study, levels of anti-COVID-19 antibodies in breast milk raised remarkably after both doses and remained elevated for six weeks. They report that these antibodies in breast milk may have powerful neutralizing and protective effects in the infant against COVID-19 infection (19).

One systematic review aimed at finding the effect of COVID-19 on breastfeeding reported that due to the presence of antibodies against Covid-19 in breastmilk, after the vaccine against the coronavirus virus has been administered, the acquisition of antibodies against COVID-19 directly through breastmilk could be beneficial for infants (20). In another systematic review, in all the cohort studies selected, breastmilk samples from lactating women who received the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine or Moderna were collected and all milk samples were positive for anti-COVID-19 antibodies as well as maternal sera. They reported that vertical-transmitted immunity is possible via breastmilk. So, the sooner COVID-19 mRNA vaccination could be more efficient (21).

According to the result of a prospective study on women who were vaccinated with two doses of the COVID-19 vaccine (Pfizer/BioNTech), the presence of IgG antibodies in breastmilk was about 7% after the first dose and increased after the second dose to 43 %, although IgA antibodies were decreased from 21% to 36% after 2nd dose. Moreover, higher titers of IgG correlated with a long breastfeeding time (22). Another Prospective cohort study was conducted to determine whether COVID-19 antibodies might be found in breast milk after vaccination. Six lactating women who were going to receive both doses of mRNA vaccine (Pfizer-BioNTech or Moderna) participated. They found that mothers vaccinated against COVID-19 produce anti-COVID-19 protein IgG and IgA in breast milk that might be protective for infants (23).

4. CONCLUSION

According to the result of this study, anti-COVID-19 antibodies are transferred to breast milk after the mother is vaccinated against COVID-19. Hence, the acquisition of antibodies against COVID-19 directly through breast milk could be beneficial for infants via vertical-transmitted immunity. However, more clinical trials are required on lactating women to find scientific guidelines.

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